

India Trade with European Union

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Abstract

In this research paper an attempt is made to study the India's trade relations with European Union. The data for India's exports to European Union and imports from European Union to the period twenty years (2000-01 to 2019-20) were compiled. Under the title of European Union, eighty percent countries are developed, therefore it is in the fitness of things that a detailed look should be taken at India's trade with European Union, as India is in a great need of increasing its exports to European Union.

Key words: Trade, Export, Import, European Union

Introduction

Profile of European Union (EU)

France, Germany, Italy, Belgium, Luxembourg, and the Netherlands established the European Economic Community (EEC) or European Community (EC) in 1957 under the Treaty of Rome. Ireland, Denmark, and the United Kingdom joined the original six members on January 1, 1973, bringing the total number of members to ten. In 1981, Greece joined, and Portugal and Spain joined in 1984. Now there are 27 members in the community. The

European Union has been its name since 1993. (EU).

Objectives of the Study

To study the India's Share of Export and Import Position with European Union.

To study the India trade with world.

To study the India trade with European Union.

Research Methodology

The present study is descriptive in nature and is based on secondary data. The data has been extracted from various sources like research articles, publications from Government of India.

1. India's Trade with World, India's Total Export and Import Picture with World

(Rs. in Lakhs)

Sr. No.	Year	Export	SGR	Import	SGR	Deficit
1	2000-01	20,357,101.09	-	23,087,276.03	-	-11.83
2	2001-02	20,901,797.34	2.68	24,519,971.85	6.21	-14.76
3	2002-03	25,513,727.66	22.06	29,720,587.39	21.21	-14.15
4	2003-04	29,336,674.75	14.98	35,910,766.36	20.83	-18.31
5	2004-05	37,533,952.62	27.94	50,106,454.02	39.53	-25.09
6	2005-06	45,641,786.15	21.60	66,040,890.32	31.80	-30.89
7	2006-07	57,177,928.52	25.28	84,050,631.32	27.27	-31.97
8	2007-08	65,586,352.18	14.71	101,231,169.92	20.44	-35.21
9	2008-09	84,075,505.87	28.19	137,443,555.44	35.77	-38.83
10	2009-10	84,553,364.38	0.57	136,373,554.75	-0.78	-38.00
11	2010-11	113,696,426.38	34.47	168,346,695.56	23.45	-32.46
12	2011-12	146,595,939.96	28.94	234,546,324.44	39.32	-37.50
13	2012-13	163,431,828.96	11.48	266,916,195.68	13.80	-38.77
14	2013-14	190,501,108.86	16.56	271,543,390.73	1.73	-29.85
15	2014-15	189,634,841.76	-0.45	273,708,657.82	0.80	-30.72
16	2015-16	171,638,440.44	-9.49	249,030,553.77	-9.02	-31.08
17	2016-17	184,943,355.34	7.75	257,767,536.67	3.51	-28.25
18	2017-18	195,651,452.80	5.79	300,103,343.34	16.42	-34.81
19	2018-19	230,772,619.38	17.95	359,467,461.18	19.78	-35.80
20	2019-20	221,985,418.10	-3.81	336,095,445.60	-6.50	-33.95
	CGR	14.94		16.41		

Source: <https://tradestat.commerce.gov.in>

The above table illustrates the detailed information of India's total trading (export

and import) development. In the year of 2018-2019 the India's highest total exports

remarks as 230772619.38 lakhs rupees by means of 17.95 percent growth rate and India's smallest total exports is exposed as 20357101.09 lakhs rupees in the year of 2000-01. So far as export is concerned the highest simple growth rate of India's total export is recorded in the year of 2010-11 that is 34.47 percent and lowest growth rate is recorded in the year of 2015-16 that is -9.49. The compound growth rate of export is marked as 14.94 and average is pointed out as 113976481.13 which are lower than the average of import. On the other hand the India's highest total import is marked as 359467461.18 lakhs rupees in the year of 2018-19 by means of 19.78 percent simple growth rate with -35.80 percent trading balance and the minimum import is marked

as 23087276.03 lakhs rupees in the year of 2000-01. The highest simple growth rate of imports is noticeable as 39.53 percent in the year of 2004-05 and the highest trading deficit of India's total trading is shown in the year of 2008-09 that is -38.83 percent. The compound growth rate of import is marked as 16.41 and average is pointed out as 170300523.11 which are higher than the average of export. The India trade with World has a CGR of 14.94 for exports and 16.41 for imports. It is observed from the above table that the compound growth rate of import is higher and the compound growth rate of export is lower. But the average of the import is higher than that of the average of export.

2. India's Trade share with European Union

India's Share of Export and Share of Import Position with European Union (Rs. in Lakhs)

Sr. No.	Year	India's Total Export	EU Total Export	%Share Export	India's Total Import	EU Total Import	%Share Import
1	2000-01	20,357,101.09	3837318.13	18.85	23,087,276.03	3430033.02	14.86
2	2001-02	20,901,797.34	3815273.37	18.25	24,519,971.85	3856646.83	15.73
3	2002-03	25,513,727.66	4549168.07	17.83	29,720,587.39	4867638.38	16.38
4	2003-04	29,336,674.75	5288997.48	18.03	35,910,766.36	5444295.83	15.16
5	2004-05	37,533,952.62	6555851.62	17.47	50,106,454.02	7071293.29	14.11
6	2005-06	45,641,786.15	8057143.33	17.65	66,040,890.32	9783291.78	14.81
7	2006-07	57,177,928.52	9612173.64	16.81	84,050,631.32	11635885.94	13.84
8	2007-08	65,586,352.18	11218387.47	17.10	101,231,169.92	13478897.48	13.31
9	2008-09	84,075,505.87	14926146.14	17.75	137,443,555.44	16773855.44	12.20
10	2009-10	84,553,364.38	14137405.60	16.72	136,373,554.75	16093725.98	11.80
11	2010-11	113,696,426.38	17680492.38	15.55	168,346,695.56	17834690.32	10.59
12	2011-12	146,595,939.96	21113466.37	14.40	234,546,324.44	23851609.83	10.17
13	2012-13	163,431,828.96	22800822.22	13.95	266,916,195.68	25019533.58	9.37
14	2013-14	190,501,108.86	25443884.86	13.36	271,543,390.73	26529945.94	9.77
15	2014-15	189,634,841.76	24558042.73	12.95	273,708,657.82	27021181.59	9.87
16	2015-16	171,638,440.44	23412111.93	13.64	249,030,553.77	25343264.03	10.18
17	2016-17	184,943,355.34	25987513.29	14.05	257,767,536.67	25969180.51	10.07
18	2017-18	195,651,452.80	28299370.11	14.46	300,103,343.34	27758603.24	9.25
19	2018-19	230,772,619.38	33443902.52	14.49	359,467,461.18	35551908.86	9.89
20	2019-20	221,985,418.10	31865538.18	14.35	336,095,445.60	31878723.41	9.49

Source: <https://tradestat.commerce.gov.in>

The above table demonstrates the detailed information of India's total trading (export and import) development and the detailed information of the total European Union trading scenario. In the year of 2018-2019 the India's highest total exports remarks as 230772619.38 lakhs rupees and India's smallest total exports is exposed as 20357101.09 lakhs rupees in the year of 2000-01. In the year of 2018-2019 the highest

total export of European Union trading remarks as 33443902.52 lakhs rupees and smallest exports of the total European Union trading is exposed as 3815273.37 lakhs rupees in the year of 2001-02. The highest share of export is 18.85 percent whereas the smallest share of export is noticed as 12.95 percent. On the other hand the India's highest total import is marked as 359467461.18 lakhs rupees in the year of

2018-19 and the minimum import is marked as 23087276.03 lakhs rupees in the year of 2000-01. The highest total European Union trading import is marked as 35551908.86 lakhs rupees in the year of 2018-19 by and minimum import is marked as 3430033.02 lakhs rupees in the year of 2000-01. The highest share of import is 16.38 percent whereas the smallest share of export is noticed as 9.25 percent. It is observed from the above table that the share of import is higher and the share of export is lower. But the India's total and EU total import is higher than that of the total of export.

Conclusions

Although EU –India trade has achieved a respectable volume of trade, it has a great scope for further improvement. There is a need for EU and India to look into policy, process, procedures and institutional action governing their trade to ensure a voluminous increase. India is an important trade partner for the European Union. The European Union's export to India is higher relative to India's export to the European Union. The ongoing European Union-India FTA (free trade agreement) negotiations have attracted much attention among trade policymakers. In contrast to most of the developing economies, India is regarded as a country with significant supply side capacity. This means that in response to any meaningful trade concessions resulting from a bilateral deal, Indian suppliers can substantially increase their exports to the European Union. In this way, the likely trade diversion in the European Union may result in reduced imports from other developing and least developed countries and increased imports from India. European Union suppliers may replace India's imports from other sources, resulting in trade diversion for India. Consequently, the overall welfare gains for India will depend on the relatively strength of the trade creation and trade diversion impacts.

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